
**THE ROLE OF FORENSIC AUDITORS IN FACILITATING A
SUSTAINABLE ACCOUNTABILITY FUTURE: A THEORETICAL
PERSPECTIVE**

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Abstract

The prominent issue militating against institutions and organizations in Nigeria is fraud. This has led to high rate of financial wastage which is highly inimical to the survival of the institutions. To curtail this trend and improve the financial workings of Nigerian institutions for sustainable future require routine forensic engagements, thus the active role of forensic auditors. The achievability of this target requires forensic auditors that are proactive in streamlining the efficiency in planning, Acting, doing and checking processes. In other words, achieving financial sustainability must be based on the PADC model of resource recovery which entails Plan, Act, Do and Check processes. Therefore, optimization of forensic auditing considers: availability and accessibility to detail information: comprehensibility in the presentation of details and facts: and independency in the gathering and compilations of details. Others are credibility in the analytical steps taken to arrive at a presentable conclusion and thoroughness in the process of the investigation and reporting. Based on these analytical perspectives, it is recommended that Forensic auditors should acquire the tactics of exploring social networking as a potent tool for information gathering necessary for opportunity identification; planned and systematic research. Also, the procedure of selecting forensic auditors should be handled by institutional independent, unit that is not directly involved in institution's financial implementation programmes.

Keywords: Forensic Auditing, Sustainable Future, Forensic Auditors Efficiency, Forensic Roles

1 Introduction

One of the clearing issues in the 21st century society is the increasing level of wastage in every facet of its workings. In other words, it may not be an

exaggeration to state that the extent of utilization of resources recently is inimical to the survival of the society organization. To say that this has transcended to the mismanagement of financial resources is to say the least. Issues abound in Nigeria related to wanton waste of resources meant for localized and generalized development of the nation. These have proportionately led to corporate scandals, corporate collapses and business failures thus eroding investors and public confidence in business activities. Sadly, these issues are not limited to government but spanned to corporate individual organizations/institutions. This bring to the fore the contentious question does the level of resource management in Nigeria has the capacity to sustain the future development?

Fundamentally, utilization of financial resources in any society could be said to be effectively and efficiently managed when it can promote healthy society, balanced with infrastructural and human capital development that can sustain not only the immediate needs but assist in serving as springboard for the outright development of the future. In other words, financial management must provide a template future sustainability. This underscores the importance of forensic auditors in the management of institutions/organization's financial performance for sustainable future. However, the cases in Nigerian institutions are different as could be seen in incessant corruption and embezzlement of funds, mismanagement of financial resources as well as unacceptable heightened financial malpractices. Hence, motivating the contemplation of the study to analytically assess and recommend measures to promote the roles of forensic auditors in facilitating a sustainable future.

2 Finance Resources Transformation for Sustainable Future

Financial transformation is one of the remarkable problems of most developing nations. This has severally led to government/corporate individuals' failure, bankruptcy, and poor implementation of projects and programmes as could be seen in folding of Nigerian banks and industries. However, to curtail the incessant financial failure, government/corporate institutions must ensure sustainability of its financial management system (Carmeli, Yitzhak and Vinerski 2008).

The concept of sustainability in financial management system entails adopting viable strategies and activities that meet the needs of the institutions as well as stakeholders today, while protecting, sustaining and enhancing the human, physical and natural resources that will be needed in the future. Dollery, Crase and Grant (2011) considered it as the ability to generate enough revenue to

meet expenses and to continue providing services at levels and quality require by the citizens. Basing from the positions of Dollery *et al.* (2011), it could be deductive to state that achieving a viable financial sustainability that can transform the existing/available resources for immediate and future accountability requires:

- i. Institutions/organizations to routinely measure the sustainability of their current behaviour as well as the direction to which they are moving toward (Gray and Wiedernan, 1999).
- ii. Identification of the size of changes requires to meets the set goals.
- iii. Effective selection of steps.
- iv. Collaboration with units' stakeholders.
- v. Efficient evaluation of the steps and processes.
- vi. Operation efficiency, enhancement in people and community commitments while minimizing the need to rely on scarce resources (Porter & Kramer, 2006).

Honadle (2003) posited that maintaining government/corporate institutions financial sustainability requires regular assessment process and cogent steps to address early warning of financial trouble. In other words, achieving financial sustainability must be based on the PADC model of resource recovery which entails Plan, Act, Do and Check processes. Plan aspect of the model can be conceptualized as surveying and assessing the entire steps and stages of goals involving financial expenditure. This streamlines the efficiency of each stage to ensure the attainment of goals. "Act" on the other hand refers to the process of reviewing the entire process to assess the strength and weakness as well as current and future needs as required to be implemented with the available financial resources. This step/process brings to the fore the areas of importance of the institution and the area that require urgent attention for the implementation of organizational goals.

In the same vein, the "Do" process refers to building institutions operational system that can handle processes/activities and ensure effectiveness and efficiency. In essence, "Do" process entails building effective internal control mechanisms that can check each stages of the process undertaken by institution financially. Meanwhile, the "Check" aspect of the model connotes routing auditing of the institution's performance which is the most vital part of the model as every institution established has target of ensuring achievement of a programmed performance. This underscores the importance of forensic auditing in institution's financial sustainability.

3 Theoretical Assessment of Forensic Auditing Optimization

The 21st century institutional porosity has brought the urgent need of routing coordination of forensic auditing if cases of bankruptcy and huge financial losses must be avoided. Forensic auditing as stated by Eyisi and Ezuwore (2014) involves fact finding process that allows the examination of knowing whether an event has actually taken place, the place, amount involve, collection of evidence, computation of the asset involve and above all, initiation of court proceedings. This connotes forensic auditing as the scientific checking of the daily process and engagements entered into by institution in a bit to attaining target as may be required for investigation, confirmation and or recommendation in the court of jurisprudence. Put differently, Institute for Forensic Auditors explains the forensic auditing to include activities of gathering, verifying, processing, analyzing of and reporting on data in order to obtain facts and or evidence in a predefined context in the area of legal financial disputes and or regulation (including fraud) and giving preventative advice (IFA, 2014). In other words, forensic auditing entails searching for fact and figures on the processes undertaken by human resource factor of an institution to cross-check the evidence of implementation of organizational/institution's target goals.

Highlighting on the objectives of forensic auditing, Eyisi and Abgaeze (2014) opined that its include

- i. improving management accountability;
- ii. improving corporate governance and the statutory audit function;
- iii. improving financial reporting system;
- iv. helping in detecting financial fraud;
- v. helping in strengthening auditors' independence;
- vi. providing additional assurance for audit committees;
- vii. assisting financial statement auditors to take greater responsibility for the detection of fraud and illegal acts when auditing financial statement due to the fact that another set of auditors (forensic auditors) would be critically evaluating their role;
- viii. giving the audit committees better tools to evaluate the quality of the financial statement audit by the external auditor.

It is worthy of mention that every institution managed by humans requires thorough forensic gap checking to ensure that opportunity is not created for fraud to take place. This is in retrospect of Donald Cressey fraud triangle model of 1953 which specify that no fraud or financial malpractices can take place without the presence of three elements of pressure, opportunity and

rationalization. Analyzing from Cressey's perspective, it could be induced that any financial failure or unsustainability act can only exist in an institution that has created opportunity for such malpractices. Erols and Congee (2011) considered opportunity in the fraud triangle as the ability to commit fraud and financial malpractices resulting from weak control system, lack of strong management oversight and failure to establish adequate procedure to detect fraudulent activity. In essence, if opportunity is not created, the pressure and rationalization of committing financial malpractice is impossible. Hence, the need for forensic auditing.

Adducing from the Cressey's theory blueprint is the fact that if one of the prominent phenomena (opportunity) exists, then a conclusion can be drawn about another phenomenon (financial malpractice or misappropriation). This implies that the best way of designing organizational structure is contingent upon the internal and external control efficiency that can lend credence to detecting financial fraud, compelling comprehensive financial statement as well as providing useful users accounting information. The resultant implications of this internal and external control efficiency are offering of highest level of assurance; provision of more accurate and scientific perspective in credibility and transparency; as well as; streamlining human resource performance optimization. This position is supported by the studies conducted by various scholars which indicated that forensic auditing offers legal review in a scientific fashion; impact on fraud prosecution and prescription of punishment for fraudsters, improve internal control system as well as financial reporting credibility and transparency (Zysman, 2004; Enofe, Idemuclia & Emmanuel, 2015).

In the same vein, Okoye, Segun and Nwankwo (2019) determined the effect of Forensic auditing on the financial performance of quoted food and beverage firms in Nigeria for the period of six years ranging from 2010-2016. The study revealed that forensic auditing has a positive and statistically significant effect on Return on Asset (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Earnings Per Share (EPS) of food and beverage firms quoted on the floor of Nigerian stock exchange at 5% level of significance. Similarly, Ukoma (2019) examined the effect of forensic auditing in reducing fraud cases in Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study sought to find out the effect forensic auditing have on internal control system, cash management system and loan processing and repayment system. Survey research design was adopted in the study and it was found that forensic auditing services is significantly associated with the internal control systems and cash management systems of DMBs but not

significantly associated with loan processing and repayment system. The studies aligned with the previous study conducted by Ogiriki and Appall (2018) that empirically analyzed the effect of forensic accounting and auditing techniques on public sector fraud detection, investigation and prevention in Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to establish the effect of the various techniques of forensic accounting on public sector fraud and secondly, to determine the effect of forensic auditing on fraud detection, investigation and prevention. The study revealed that the relationship between forensic accounting and auditing techniques and public sector fraud detection, investigation and prevention in Nigeria is quite significant. The study therefore concludes that forensic accounting and auditing techniques is a major panacea to the fraudulent activities experienced in the Nigerian public sector. It was recommended among others that government should consider providing more fraud hotlines, improve the whistleblowing policy and establish forensic accounting department in the public sector in order to enhance the fraud detection, investigation and prevention mechanism in the public sector.

Onodi, Okafor and Onyali (2015) researched on the impact of forensic investigative methods on corporate fraud deterrence in Nigerian banks using primary and secondary data sourced from reports on fraud and forgery in the banking sector. The result revealed that there is a significant relationship between the forensic investigative methods and corporate fraud deterrence; that expert services of forensic investigators are normally required in the prosecution of fraud, but majority of the audit and accounting personnel in Nigeria are suffering from poor perception and knowledge of forensic investigative methods. Adeniyi (2015) examined the effect of forensic auditing on financial fraud in Nigerian (DMBs) banks and audit firms in Abeokuta, Ogun State. The results of the study revealed that forensic audit has significant effect on financial fraud control in Nigerian (DMBs) and that forensic audit reports significantly enhances court adjudication on financial fraud in Nigeria. The study concluded that the application of forensic audit to tackle financial fraud in Nigerian (DMBs) is still at the infant stage, and recommended that organisations should have a strong internal control system in place to reduce the recurrence of fraud.

Nevertheless, efficiency in the operational process and effectiveness in the part of personnel is essential for professionalism to be optimized in forensic auditing. Therefore, optimization of forensic auditing considers:

- i. Availability and accessibility to detail information.
- ii. Comprehensibility in the presentation of details and facts

- iii. Independency in the gathering and compilations of details.
- iv. Credibility in the analytical steps taken to arrive at a presentable conclusion.
- v. Thoroughness in the process of the investigation and reporting.

It is contingent on these optimization conditions/consideration that audit expectation gap that exposes corporate institutions to opportunity to committers of financial malpractices and failure can be avoided.

4 Forensic Auditors Roles in Financial Resource Sustainability

The pervasiveness of financial malpractice/failure in every facet of Nigerian economy has led to unsustainability in institutional, infrastructural and human capital development. Kasum (2007) exaggerates that "from the common man in the street to the politician; from organizational directors/executives to the flow cleaner; from the legal officers to the law enforcement personnel; from the civil servants to the school teacher from the trader in the market to the hawkers on the street, the tendency for fraud and fraud related crime is never ending". This describes the extent of existence of fraud or financial malpractices in the society, thus calling for the pertinent roles of forensic auditors.

Forensic auditors are considered as the guarantors of financial resource sustainability. They are persons with expertise and skills for investigation on financial matter which may be used in law COUH (Eyisi and Ezuwore, 2014). In this respect, forensic auditors can be categorized as train personnel with requisite skills to conduct investigation and analyzing financial transaction authenticity, alteration or counterfeiting for accurate reporting for litigation. Boritz, Kotchetora and Robinson (2008) while analyzing on the duties of organization's internal auditors and their limitations inferred that forensic auditors give credence to financial appropriation and reporting, conduct fraud detection, calculate economic damages and expert witness, as such stand better chance of detecting fraud than the conventional auditors. Messier (2000) considered forensic auditors as fraud examiners trained by Association of Certified Fraud Examiners on areas which covers fraudulent financial transactions, legal elements of fraud investigation, criminology and ethics. Thus, they are trained to investigate, guide and restore the investors' confidence on the operation optimization as well as building credibility of the institutions. Be that as it may, building a sustainable future in financial appropriation and management requires forensic auditors that can:

- I. investigate issues/cases both objectively and from the point of organizational establishment to professional conclusion.

- ii. render services above self-interest.
- iii. Align fact with figures using diverse financial security protocols.
- iv. ensure strict consistency and adherence to principles of independency.
- v. ensure highest level of loyalty to the exposure of any fraudulent gap that can deter implementation of institutional goals.
- vi. ensure specificity in the assessment of tasks assign and adhere to the obligation of utmost responsibilities.

The aforementioned disposition of the forensic auditor has the potency of implementing the PADC models in minimizing (if not completely eradicating) fraud and tactics that stamped good governance.

5 Conclusion and Recommendations

The actualization of good governance as well as ensuring sustainability in the provision of quality services through absolute implementation of led clown plans of any institution is subject to the level of thoroughness in "planning, acting, doing and checking" processes by forensic auditors. In essence, the sustainability of future development of any institution or system depends on forensic auditors with creativity that is closely related and individual ability to connect the dots and swift understanding of information ambiguity as well as recognize any emerging patterns of fraud. This underscores the essentialities and the roles of the forensic auditors in protecting the plans and programmes implementation of an institution.

In view of the findings and conclusion above, the following recommendations are hereby made:

- i. Forensic auditors should acquire the tactics of exploring social networking as a potent tool for information gathering necessary for opportunity identification; planned and systematic research,
- ii. Institution that employs the services of forensic auditors must accept absolute adherence to the principle of outright independency of the auditors to ensure stringent implementation of forensic duties according to the PADC model.
- iii. The procedure of selecting forensic auditors should be handle by institutional independent unit that is not directly involved in institution's financial implementation programmes.

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